

THE ROLE OF MICRO-GAS IN THE ENERGY OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE STAGES OF THEIR DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. During the meeting of the video selector dedicated to the priority tasks for the expansion of the use of renewable energy held under the chairmanship of our president, it was noted that areas for the construction of micro and small hydroelectric power plants were determined in the regions, and 200 projects with a total of 56 megawatts were developed. Because small hydro facilities are one of the most effective areas of alternative energy development. Such power plants are especially needed in remote and hard-to-reach places with limited access to transmission lines. Small rivers, canals, and waterbeds from reservoirs are convenient sources for this.

Key words: gies, energy, energy sources, consumers, rotor, solar panels, development of our country.

Introduction. According to international standards, a micro hydropower plant is a hydropower device with a capacity of 0.1 kW to 100 kW, which consists of a turbine, belt and reduction gears, and an asynchronous generator. Hydro turbines generate power due to the rapid flow of water. The faster the water flows, the more

electricity it produces, and it does not damage the natural landscape and environment during construction and operation. It does not have a negative effect on water quality, that is, it does not lose its original natural properties. Therefore, they are useful in all aspects and are useful in generating relatively cheap electricity. This requires the construction of new hydroelectric power plants and the modernization of existing ones in different regions of our country.

The community is working on 20 major projects with a total additional 740 megawatts of power in 2022-2026. In particular, in 2022, 8 projects with a capacity of 258 megawatts, including 4 new construction and modernization projects, 8 projects with a capacity of 76 megawatts and 4 more in 2023-2024 are planned. A list of 200 micro hydropower projects planned to be implemented with the participation of the private sector was created in order to ensure the implementation of the decision on additional measures for development. Meetings and interviews were held with entrepreneurs who expressed the initiative to implement them. In this way, it is planned to produce 180 thousand kilowatt hours of electricity per year on the basis of projects with a total capacity of 56 megawatts. Another important point is that

attractive tariffs have been set for the initial purchase price of electricity provided by hydroelectric power stations up to 500 kilowatts. Surplus electricity from solar and wind up to 1 megawatt and small hydropower plants up to 5 megawatts will be purchased by the state for at least 10 years.

Summary. In conclusion. In our people, there is a multi-meaning wisdom that the water that flows from your side has no value. Hydro engineers, on the contrary, say that it is very useful in all aspects, and the projects they are implementing confirm this. For example, since the Zomin micro-hydroelectric power station in Jizzakh region and the cascade of 5 compact hydro-structures in Samarkand region were put into operation, thousands of households began to be supplied with uninterrupted electricity.

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